

Estimation of the Contaminant Risk Level of Petroleum Residues Applying FDA Techniques

Miguel Flores, Ana Escobar, Luis Horna, and Lucía Carrión

Abstract—In the process of oil extraction, specifically in the refinement and industrialization of hydrocarbons, as is known, multiple wastes are highly polluting for the soil, water and air.

In this work, the risk level of these wastes in affected areas is estimated thanks to the application of statistical models in the field of functional data analysis. These models have been implemented in a statistical software called *RStudio* that allows an early measurement and evaluation of the level of risk by using semiquantitative and quantitative methods. This measurement is carried out by the staff of PETROECUADOR close to the affected place. It was used the laser-induced fluorescence technique (LIF). The data obtained using this technique was used to adjust the following models: Generalized Functional Linear Model (MLFG), which makes it possible to classify the spectrum generated in two pollution levels: Low and High. Functional linear regression model with scalar response and functional explanatory variable with the aim of directly estimating the percentage of contamination level. With these results it is verified that the shape of the laser fluorescence spectrum is highly related to the gasoline content in the sample.

Index Terms—Quality Control, Generalized Linear Functional Model, Linear Regression, Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

The filtration of oil (or its derivatives), transport and diffusion-dispersion are processes whose study is of vital importance due to the great impact they have on human activity and the environment.

The filtration of petroleum in soils causes a level of pollution that is a very complex problem to evaluate, this depends mainly on the following elements: soil type, porosity, hydraulic conductivity, and petroleum properties such as density and viscosity.[1]

For this reason, an important task is to determine the state of the system at all times, and as a priority at the initial moment, since it would allow the application of corrective measures in the ecosystem in a more efficient way.[7]

Oil is made up of a variety of compounds, some of which produce fluorescence when illuminated with ultraviolet light. The fluorescence of the petroleum depends to a great extent on its chemical composition (Celander, Fredricsson, Galle, and Svanberg, 1988). For this reason there are analytical techniques for the characterization of crude oil, in the parts

that the intensity and life time of the fluorescence are related to the chemical composition and density (API) of the oil.[7]

If we combine a source of ultraviolet laser light, a spectrometer and oil, we will have a system to detect the presence of petroleum, such as contaminated lands (O'Neill, RA, Buja-Bijunos, L., Rayner, DM, 1980). Laser light produces fluorescence when there is oil in the earth, which is detected using the spectrometer. As each variety of oil has a characteristic fluorescence spectrum, fluorescence techniques are often used for identification.[1] The data obtained by this technique are used in the first instance to solve a problem of supervised classification and then to carry out a forecast of the level of contamination.

Among the statistical techniques that are used to solve a classification problem are: discriminant analysis, logistic regression and cluster analysis, depending on the objective. For example, in Anderson, Farrar, Thoms, (2009) determines the contamination of anthropogenic metals in the soil using the technique of discriminant analysis with clustered chemical concentrations. In the case of the prediction process, Lopez (2014) applies a linear regression in order to predict the air pollution of carbon dioxide produced by Hawaii's Mauna Loa volcano, in this case time is the independent variable and pollution is the dependent variable.

The statistical techniques mentioned are traditional and multivariate techniques, however, in recent times technological changes has been able to measure data in a faster and more precise way, and thanks to this evolution, it is possible to work with the functional form of the data.[2]

In this work, statistical techniques of functional data analysis (Functional data Analyzes - FDA -) are used. Specifically, a Generalized Functional Linear Model is applied to solve the classification problem and a Linear Regression Model with scalar response and functional explanatory variable to estimate the level of contamination. One of the advantages of using FDA is reducing the influence of noise or observation errors. (Ramsay, & Silverman, 2005).

Classification of functional data is one of the major branches of the FDA (Functional Data Analysis), there are two types of classification that are: supervised and unsupervised. In the case of unsupervised classification, its objective will be to make groups as homogeneous as possible, and at the same time the most distinct among them (Noguerales, 2010); the most common technique is clustering and the method for performing such technique is k-means.

For the supervised classification there are different classifiers that will help to classify the base between them: Linear Discriminant, k-NN (nearest neighbor method), Kernel,

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Table I
SAMPLES MADE FOR MFLG ADJUSTMENT AND VALIDATION

Sample	Level	Total	Sample 2	Level 2	Total 2
GE1	0.3	2	GE8	9.1	2
GE2	0.4	2	GA15	16.67	2
GE3	0.5	2	GE9	16.7	2
GA1	1.48	2	GE10	37.5	2
GA3	1.48	2	GA19	37.5	2
GE4	1.5	2	GE11	50	2
GE5	2.4	2	GA23	50	2
GA5	2.44	2	GE12	75	2
GE6	3.8	2	GE13	83.3	2
GA8	3.85	2	GA26	83.33	2
GE7	6.1	2	GE14	100	2
GA13	6.1	2	GA30	100	2
GA14	9.09	2			

PLS (generalized linear models), Generalized linear models (Noguerales, 2010).

A recent application of a Generalized Linear Functional Model can be found in Flores, Saltos and Castillo-Paz (2016), where the types of cancer are classified by DNA information.

In this study, the generalized functional linear model was used to classify the contamination level of the hydrocarbon residues, with a variable binary response. This model assumes that the content of the solid element remains constant and that it is indeformable.

It is important to note that the model has already been integrated in a software that interacts with the laser spectrometer, built by the team of engineers of the project developed by the National Polytechnic School of Ecuador.

On the other hand, the functional linear regression model with scalar response and functional explanatory variable, the model is used as predictor. This class of models has been applied to regional analysis associations as an alternative to standard multiple regression models (Luo, Zhu, Xiong (2012)).

For the development of the models, 25 tests (with two replicates) were carried out, which are differentiated by the percentage (level) of gasoline in the sample (see Table 1). For this work, if a spectrum has a gas percentage less than or equal to 10% it is classified in the low pollution group. Otherwise it is classified in the high pollution group. The model allows to consider any other level of gasoline to discriminate between spectra corresponding to samples with a low or high contamination.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology used in this study with functional data is that described in Bande and Fuente (2012), which consists of the following stages:

- 1) Explore and describe the functional data set highlighting its most important characteristics.
- 2) Explain and model:
 - a) Find the relationship between a dependent variable and an independent variable using regression models

b) Solve the problem of Supervised or Non-Supervised Classification of a set of data regarding some characteristic.

3) Contrast, validation and prediction.

But before describing the stages of the methodology is given a definition of a functional random variable.

Let X random variable it is functional if it takes values in the space which can be normalized and semi normalized. (Bande and Fuente, 2012).

One set of functional data $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ is the observation of n functional variables $\{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$ Identically distributed (Bande and Fuente, 2012).

The most aware to work with functional data is to determine the space where it works to use right statistical techniques.

Let $T = [a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$. It is generally assumed that there are elements of :

$$\mathcal{L}^2 = \{X : T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \text{ such that } \int_T |X|^2 dx < \infty\} \quad (1)$$

A. FDA exploratory analysis

The first step is the exploratory analysis of the data to make their characteristics known and know exactly how to manipulate them.

The methods of representation are: decrementation and the choice of a reduced basis of functions. One way to represent the functional data is in a nonparametric way. And in most cases this is the best representation.

In this work, we used the B-spline base to represent the functional data. And in most cases this is the best representation. It is given by a smoothing matrix S :

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{h} K(t_i - t_j)h \quad (2)$$

Where h is the bandwidth, which is calculated with cross-validation.

There are different kernel types $K()$, however the most used is **Gaussian**

$$K(u) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \exp\left(-\frac{u^2}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

This is to approximate and have the best representation of \mathcal{X} :

$$\hat{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n s_i(x) Y_i \quad (4)$$

There are different methods for calculating $s_i()$: the nearest neighbor, Nadaraya-Watson, local linear regression.

X is defined as the functional variable of interest, spectrum generated through the LIF technique, which takes values in a normalized (or semi-normalized) space F , and is considered as functional data to the results of the 25 tests represented as the set x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n that come from n functional variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n identically distributed as X .

Definition 2. A base is a set of known functions $(\Phi_k)_{k \in N}$ such that any function can be approximated as well as desired by a linear combination of K of them with sufficiently large K .

In this way functional observation can be approximated as

Figure 1. Functional average:

Figure 2. Functional variance:

$$X(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n c_k F_k(t) \quad (5)$$

The type of base will depend on the nature of the data, it is very common to use B-Spline bases, second step is to describe the functional data, functional exploratory analysis is used, in which several estimators such as the mean and the functional variance.

Then, depending on the purpose of the study, techniques such as functional regression, classification models, and others are used.

The present document aims to provide an overview of these techniques, in order to present the usefulness of their application to the environmental context.

The results are obtained through the statistical software R and its packets, such as the packet, '*fda.usc*'.

The mean and functional variance are defined below: Let $x_i(t)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ be a sample of functional data curves, the mean and variance are given by (Plazola, 2013):

The FDA concepts and techniques used in this paper can be found in the books of Ramsay and Silverman, 2002 and Ramsay and Silverman, 2006. In both cases, all the included techniques are restricted to the space of \mathcal{L}^2 functions (the Hilbert space of all square integrable functions over a certain interval). The book by Ferraty and Vieu is another important reference that incorporates non-parametric approaches, as well as the use of other theoretical tools like Semi-norms that allow us to deal with norms or metric spaces.

X is defined as the functional variable of interest, spectrum generated through the LIF technique, which takes values in a

Figure 3. Spectra by level of contamination

normalized (or semi-normalized) space F , and is considered as functional data to the results of the 25 tests represented as the set x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n that come from n functional variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n identically distributed as X .

The functional data are discretized in a total of 3'648 points that are in the range [176.39, 890.62]. These are represented by the set of points t_j . In Figure 1 we can see in blue color the spectra of low level and in red color the spectros of high level.

It can be seen from the figure that the spectra tend to have the same shape however the spectra of high level have a greater amplitude than the low ones and it is increasing in relation to the percentage of gasoline that is in the sample. This varies from 16.67% to 100% (greater than 10%); on the other hand, the amplitude of the spectra of the low level samples are decreasing according to the percentage of gasoline in the sample. A spectrum is considered with a low level of pollution if the percentage of gasoline is less than 10%, that is from 3% to 9.1%.

For the representation of the functional data, a B-spline base was used using the *fda.usc* package of the statistical software R (Bande and Fuente, 2012).

B. Generalized Functional Linear Model (MFLG)

Once the spectra are represented to functional data, a Generalized Linear Functional Model (MFLG) is fitted to estimate the probability that it belongs to one of the two groups. For the adjustment and implementation of the model, the '*fregre.glm*' function of the *fda.usc* package of the statistical software R was used.

The MFLG is also known in the literature as Functional Logistic Regression (FLR).

The model explains the relationship between Y (binary response) and a functional covariate $X(t)$ with representation based on $X(t)$ and $\beta(t)$. Π_i is the probability of occurrence of the event $Y_i = 1$, which in this case corresponds to a high contamination, conditioned to the covariate $X_i(t)$, which is expressed as follows:

$$Y_i = \pi_i + \epsilon_i, \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

$$\pi_i = P \left[Y = \frac{1}{x_i(t)} : t \in T \right] \quad (7)$$

$$= \frac{\exp(\int_T X_i(t)\beta(t)dt)}{1 + \exp(\int_T X_i(t)\beta(t)dt)} \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (8)$$

Where ϵ_i are independent errors with zero mean. It is defined as a functional covariate the spectrum denoted by: $X = X(t)$, and as a scalar (binary) response variable the

	High	Low
High	6	0
Low	0	5

type of pollution denoted by Y (0 = Low pollution, 1 = High pollution).

In this case, since the MFLG works with a binary response variable, this model provides a classification rule for the type of contamination (Bayes rule).

C. Linear regression with scalar response variable and functional explanatory variable

For this model the objective will be to understand how a response variable Y being this scalar is related to a vector of variables $X \in \mathbb{R}^p$

Therefore, the regression model is defined as follows (Ramírez, 2014),

$$Y = \langle X, \beta \rangle + \epsilon \quad (9)$$

$$Y = \langle X, \beta \rangle + \epsilon \quad (10)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \int_T x(t)\beta(t)dt + \epsilon \quad (11)$$

In our case study we will analyze the following model

Where, $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ we denote the usual internal product defined in \mathcal{L}^2 and ϵ is the random error with mean zero and variance σ^2 . Specifically, we will perform a non-parametric functional regression model. An alternative to model (5) is

$$y_t = r(X_t(t)) + \epsilon_t \quad (12)$$

Where, the unknown real soft function is estimated using the Kernel estimate.

For the regression model it is considered as a scalar response variable the percentage of water presented by gasoline and our functional explanatory variable is the spectrum. To obtain the corresponding estimates, the *'fregre.np'* function of the *'fda.usc'* package has been used.

D. Validation of the models

For the validation of the statistical models, two samples are used.

A sample of training and validation. For each test taken, two replicates of the spectrum were obtained.

These are used as follows: one of the replicas is used for the training of the model and the other replica for the validation of the model.

In this work, to carry out the validation of the model a confusion matrix is used, with the following structure:

High Low / High True False negatives /Low False positives True negatives).

Where, true positives and true negatives correspond to correctly classified spectra in high and low contamination respectively, while false negatives and false positives are misclassified spectra by our model; Using the data of the spectra we obtain:

As seen in the previous matrix, the model has an efficiency of 100%.

On the other hand, for the validity of the functional linear regression model with scalar response and functional explanatory variable, the coefficient of determination R^2 was used, where a value of 99% was obtained, this implies that the model correctly explains the variability of the data in that percentage. We also calculate the mean absolute percentage error(MAPE) with nonparametric regressions, 7% was obtained.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prior to the modeling, an exploratory analysis of the data in the functional field has been carried out, i.e. the mean and functional variance for all data, as well as for the High and Low groups, have been estimated. The way to estimate these descriptive measures is in Gonzalez-Manteiga and Vieu, 2007.

From Figure 4, it can be seen that there is a clear distinction between the defined groups. This result facilitates and confirms the use of a functional supervised classification model.

In Figure 5, a graph of probabilities resulting from applying the GLFM model is presented.

Where it is appreciated that the spectra with a percentage less than 10% are classified as low level while the rest of the spectra are classified as high level. Therefore, the model correctly classifies 100% of the spectra in each group (Low and High). Figure 6 shows the level of contamination that the oil sample will present. It is important to mention that several tests were done with different methods trying to find the one that fit the best. It is also observed the two curves, both the estimation with the model and the actual pollution, coincide in almost every point.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

As mentioned in the introduction each sample has two replicates, one of which is used for model estimation and the other for its validation. In the case of the sample for the estimation we have that the percentage of correctly classified spectra in each group (Low and High) is 100%, while for the validation sample the percentage of correctly classified spectra is 99% with a MAPE of 7%.

It has been verified that the shape of the laser fluorescence spectrum is highly related to the gasoline content of the sample.

Figure 4. Functional descriptive measures by level of contamination.

Figure 5. Estimated probabilities.

Figure 6. Actual pollution level vs. estimated by the functional regression model.

Therefore, due to its functional nature, the application of supervised FDA classification techniques provides a reliable solution for the identification of a high or low risk of contamination in potentially affected areas.

When applying the functional regression model, we have managed to explain the 99% R^2 of the variability, in addition to reach this result has been tested with several models. The corresponding validation tests of the model were also performed, which were statistically significant.

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